

CTSA Program Center for Data to Health Response: NIH Requests Public Comment on a Draft Policy for Data Management and Sharing and Supplemental Draft Guidance

- Request for Public Comments on a DRAFT NIH Policy for Data Management and Sharing and Supplemental DRAFT Guidance ([Document Number: 2019-24529](#))
- Complete information about the draft Policy and draft supplemental guidance can be found on the [NIH OSP website](#).

PROMPT	CD2H Response
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Name of Organization	CTSA Program Center for Data to Health
Type of Data of Primary Interest	Select from: Genomic, Clinical, Imaging, Basic Biomedical, Qualitative, Other
Type of Organization	Select from: N/A, University, Non-profit Research Org, Biotech/Pham Co, Prof Org/Assoc, Patient Advocacy Org, Health Care Delivery Org, Govt agency
Role	Select from: member of public, Scientific Researcher, Patient Advocate, Bioethicist/Social Science Researcher, Institutional Official, Govt Official, Medical Provider, other
Domain of Research Most Important to You or Your Organization	Translational medicine, informatics, data science, team science

DRAFT NIH Policy for Data Management and Sharing

Section I: Purpose (limit: 8000 characters)

The NIH Policy for Data Management and Sharing (herein referred to as the Policy) reinforces NIH's longstanding commitment to making the results and outputs of the research that it funds and conducts available to the public. Data sharing enables researchers to rigorously test the validity of research findings, strengthen analyses through combined datasets, reuse hard-to-generate data, and explore new frontiers of discovery. In addition, NIH emphasizes the importance of good data management practices, which provide the foundation for effective data sharing and improve the reproducibility and reliability of research findings. NIH encourages data management and data sharing practices consistent with the NIH Plan for Increasing Access to Scientific Publications and Digital Scientific Data from NIH Funded Scientific Research and the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles.

To promote effective and efficient data management and data sharing, NIH expects researchers to manage scientific data resulting from NIH-funded or conducted research and prospectively plan for which scientific data will be preserved and shared. Under this Policy, individuals and entities would be required to provide a Data Management and Sharing Plan (Plan) describing how scientific data will be managed, including when and where the scientific data will be preserved and shared, prior to initiating the research study. Shared data should be made accessible in a timely manner for use by the research community and the broader public.

This Policy is intended to establish expectations for Data Management and Sharing Plans upon which other NIH Institutes, Centers and Offices (ICO) may supplement as appropriate.

CD2H RESPONSE

Recommendation Ia: Clearly communicate the NIH Policy for Data Management and Sharing in the context of downstream users of the data

In order for the research community and broader public to make effective use of research data, the providers of this data must consider the needs of these secondary consumers. One such need is timeliness in sharing research data. Reproducing and replicating research studies can be more readily achieved if the data are released as soon as possible upon a project's completion, and after all human participants' privacy rights and identifiable information have been sufficiently considered and protected in a dataset. Throughout the Draft Policy for Data Management and Sharing, no recommendation is given for either the minimum or maximum amount of time that has elapsed since a study's completion at which the study's data must be shared. A general recommendation such as those promulgated by the AHRQ and NOAA could be made, requiring data sharing either upon publication or 24-36 months after initial data collection. As section VI of the policy states, not all data collected from human subjects will be eligible for sharing, as can be outlined in the Data Management and Sharing Plan of individual awards. However, the existence of such exceptions would not preclude a general recommendation for a data or milestone-based deadline for sharing of research data for the majority of funded studies, barring only those studies for which data cannot, for legal, ethical, or privacy reasons, be shared.

Recommendation Ib: Clearly define and describe best practices of data management and sharing and infrastructure that is recommended to be made available for this purpose at the institution level (also see Supplemental DRAFT Guidance: [Elements of a NIH Data Management and Sharing Plan](#))

This section notes that the NIH "emphasizes the importance of good data management practices," as such practices will enable reproducibility of studies with the original data by other researchers. However, beyond describing in the Data Management and Sharing Plan how data from a research study will be managed, no guidance is provided for best practices in data management. Data management will be most effective and comprehensively practiced when it is a collaboration between principal investigators, their affiliated organizations, and research funders. To ensure shared data meets a basic standard for sharing and reproducibility, the NIH can espouse guidelines and best practices in research data management, offering resources and consultations for those embarking on these efforts for the first time. The NIH can also provide clear recommendations for making data FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable). For instance, a basic level of metadata descriptors for shared data can be required, which allows for findability within repositories; a requirement for a DOI for datasets deposited in repositories for sharing can ensure accessibility; usage of controlled vocabularies for metadata description in repositories, for interoperability, can be required and assisted with links, guidance and recommendations; and clear community standards for data description and guidance on licenses to assign to funded datasets can help NIH-funded data assets to be reusable. Within many extramurally-funded organizations, infrastructure already exists to support researchers in data management, making data FAIR, and sharing data. This infrastructure frequently involves academic health centers' health sciences libraries, leveraging the expertise of data librarians and data scientists who provide trainings, consultations, and assistance in sharing data through tools such as institutional repositories, which themselves are assets often administered and maintained by libraries. Further, making data reusable often requires the application and development of standards. This requires specialized expertise, which should be documented, where relevant, as part of the Data Management and Sharing plan and how such activities will be supported within the full course of the proposed research.

Additionally, recommendations about the temporal aspect of data management should be addressed: how long is the data expected to be available, and what are the expectations of NIH regarding sustainability of datasets and the dependencies that make it FAIR (Ex: stable repository, software integral for effective reuse, maintenance of ontologies).

In order to ensure data management/sharing best practices across the institution, NIH should encourage institutions to foster and support collaborations between investigators, libraries and research computing departments.

Section II: Definitions (limit: 8000 characters)

For the purposes of this Policy, terms are defined as follows:

- Data Management and Sharing Plan (Plan): A plan describing how scientific data will be managed, preserved, and shared with others (e.g., researchers, institutions, the broader public), as appropriate.
- Data Management: The process of validating, organizing, securing, maintaining, and processing scientific data, and of determining which scientific data to preserve.
- Data Sharing: The act of making scientific data available for use by others (e.g., researchers, institutions, the broader public).
- Metadata: Data describing scientific data that provide additional information to make such scientific data more understandable (e.g., date, independent sample and variable description, outcome measures, and any intermediate, descriptive, or phenotypic observational variables).
- Scientific Data: The recorded factual material commonly accepted in the scientific community as necessary to validate and replicate research findings, regardless of whether the data are used to support scholarly publications. Scientific data do not include laboratory notebooks, preliminary analyses, completed case report forms, drafts of scientific papers, plans for future research, peer reviews, communications with colleagues, or physical objects, such as laboratory specimens. NIH expects that reasonable efforts will be made to digitize all scientific data.

CD2H RESPONSE

Recommendation IIa: Make a comprehensive glossary of data management and sharing available.

Best practices in data management and resource sharing impact a broad range of stakeholders and are necessarily found across a wide range of disciplinary boundaries, including computer science, information science, digital scholarship, economics, ethics, linguistics, philosophy, and the many different disciplines where data are generated and need to be managed and shared. Given the broad influence of different disciplines on the data generated as well as on the infrastructure needed to manage and share it, a glossary of terms will help to clarify terms and their definitions and ensure that collaborators have a shared understanding of concepts. The data glossary can be something quite simple with terms and definitions, such as <https://www.data.gov/glossary> and should be supplemented with source materials as a primer for self-paced learning and reference. Likewise, science is becoming ever more interdisciplinary, libraries are the one place where a global view of research data can be obtained, and who have the knowledge to manage data at both the disciplinary and general level. Libraries can play a role with orientation, training, and technical support.

Recommendation IIb: Modify and supplement terms and definitions as follows:

- Data Management and Sharing Plan (Plan): A plan describing how scientific data will be managed, preserved, and shared with others (e.g., researchers, institutions, the broader public), as appropriate.
 - No substantive changes recommended; delete “as appropriate”.
- Data Management: The process of validating, organizing, securing, maintaining, and processing scientific data, and of determining which scientific data to preserve.
 - The definition for data management definition should also include the concept of “curating” to reflect the ongoing and active process of data management throughout the data lifecycle. The University of Illinois’ Graduate School of Library and Information Science defines data curation as “the active and ongoing management of data through its life cycle of interest and usefulness.”
- Data Sharing: The act of making scientific data available for use by others (e.g., researchers, institutions, the broader public).
 - No changes recommended

- **Metadata:** Data describing scientific data that provide additional information to make such scientific data more understandable (e.g., date, independent sample and variable description, outcome measures, and any intermediate, descriptive, or phenotypic observational variables).
 - The metadata definition should be supplemented to reflect the role that metadata can play in supporting FAIR -- Metadata: Data describing scientific data that provide additional information to make such scientific data more findable, accessible, interoperable, reproducible (FAIR), and understandable (e.g., date, independent sample and variable description, outcome measures, and any intermediate, descriptive, or phenotypic observational variables).

- **Scientific Data:** The recorded factual material commonly accepted in the scientific community as necessary to validate and replicate research findings, regardless of whether the data are used to support scholarly publications. Scientific data do not include laboratory notebooks, preliminary analyses, completed case report forms, drafts of scientific papers, plans for future research, peer reviews, communications with colleagues, or physical objects, such as laboratory specimens. NIH expects that reasonable efforts will be made to digitize all scientific data.
 - It is important that the definition of Scientific Data remain worded as it is “...regardless of whether the data are used to support scholarly publications” to clearly communicate that the published paper should not be considered the sole driving force in how we consider Scientific Data and its generation, curation, analysis, dissemination, and preservation - especially given the evolving landscape of scholarly communication and options for dissemination of scholarship and knowledge.
 - The recommendation to digitize all scientific data should likely be defined separately, along with community best practices for digitization to guide users. Support materials should include a consideration of format, description, metadata, preservation, rights, etc. and any hardware and software considerations as needed as to maximize the chances for survival and continued accessibility of digitized content well into the future. Support should also consider person-hours needed to digitize materials not born-digital.
 - Data, well-documented code, instructions for running analyses, workflows, and any other materials used to produce a publication and its figures/tables should be packaged and versioned so that the publication is computationally reproducible. There are many existing tools that can make this possible including reproducibility-friendly programming environments (e.g., Jupyter Notebook, R Studio), software containers, and virtual machines.

Section III: Scope (limit: 8000 characters)

This Policy applies to all research, funded or conducted in whole or in part by NIH, that results in the generation of scientific data. This includes research funded or conducted by extramural grants, contracts, intramural research projects, or other funding agreements regardless of NIH funding level or funding mechanism.

CD2H RESPONSE

Recommendation III: Accommodate and support access of research objects beyond data.

Considering the great diversity of work across the biomedical research spectrum, we recommend that the scope is augmented to accommodate a recommendation from NIH that the wide range of research objects created during NIH funded research (beyond those that impact the production, curation, preservation, and dissemination, and downstream use of data e.g., protocols, training or engagement materials, technical reports, supplemental materials, survey instruments, etc.) are accommodated in data management and sharing plans more broadly. This will better enhance the visibility of research efforts, promote people and their expertise, support attribution of their work, aid the discovery and accessibility of datasets and other digital objects by the international scientific community, and support open and FAIR science. Investigators should be encouraged to make any resources generated with support from public funds freely accessible and repurposable by the public.

Section IV: Effective Date(s) (limit: 8000 characters)

The effective date of this Policy and subsequent implementation deadlines are dependent upon feedback on this proposal. This Policy is proposed to be effective for NIH-funded or conducted research, including:

- Competing grant applications that are submitted to NIH for a future receipt date or subsequent receipt dates (date yet to be determined);
- Proposals for contracts that are submitted to NIH on or after a future date (date yet to be determined);
- NIH Intramural research conducted on or after a future date (date yet to be determined); and
- Other funding agreements (e.g., Other Transactions) that are executed on or after a future date (date yet to be determined), unless otherwise stipulated by NIH.

RESPONSE: No recommendation.

Section V: Requirements (limit: 8000 characters)

This Policy would require:

- Submission of a Data Management and Sharing Plan (Plan) outlining how scientific data will be managed and shared, considering any potential restrictions or limitations.
- Compliance with the NIH ICO-approved Plan, prospectively describing effective management and timely sharing of scientific data (as appropriate) and accompanying metadata resulting from NIH-funded or conducted research.

The funding NIH ICO may request additional or specific information to be included within the Plan in order to meet expectations for data management and data sharing in support of programmatic priorities or to expand the utility of the scientific data generated from the research. Costs associated with data management and data sharing may be allowable under the budget for the proposed project (see below, Supplemental DRAFT Guidance: Allowable Costs for Data Management and Sharing).

CD2H RESPONSE

Recommendation V: Clearly define the language and expectations around cost, responsible parties, and free or otherwise supported resources that would allow an investigator to comply with the Policy.

Clearly addressing questions such as: Is there a cap? Can costs be built in as direct or are they considered as part of the indirect? Can dedicated staff members be hired to the team for data management?

NIH funding is already highly weighted towards R1 institutions and previous NIH grant awardees, often leaving out smaller institutions that are doing excellent work in underserved and diverse populations, and by researchers from underserved and diverse backgrounds. Requiring a resource-heavy DMP without explicit understanding that this activity will be supported in some way by the NIH will place yet another barrier to funding important and ground-breaking research that is already underfunded and difficult to discover because of lack of resources.

Section VI: Data Management and Sharing Plans (limit: 8000 characters)

Researchers with NIH-funded or conducted research projects resulting in the generation of scientific data are required to submit a Plan to the funding NIH ICO as part of Just-in-Time for extramural awards, as part of the technical evaluation for contracts, as part of the NIH Intramural Annual Report, or prior to release of funds for other funding agreements. Plans should explain how scientific data generated by a research study will be managed and which of these scientific data will be shared. Plans may be updated by researchers (with appropriate NIH ICO approval) during regular reporting intervals if changes are necessary or at the request of the NIH ICO to reflect changes in the previously documented approach to data management and data sharing throughout the research project, as appropriate. NIH encourages shared scientific data to be made available as long as it is deemed useful to the Start Printed Page 60401research community or the public.

Plans should also identify strategies or approaches to ensure data security and compliance with privacy protections are in place throughout the life of the scientific data. NIH may make Plans publicly available.

NIH prioritizes the responsible management and sharing of scientific data derived from human participants. Applicable Federal, Tribal, state, and local laws, regulations, statutes, guidance, and institutional policies dictate how research involving human participants should be conducted and how the scientific data derived from human participants should be used. Researchers proposing to generate scientific data derived from human participants should outline in their Plans how human participants' privacy, rights, and confidentiality will be protected, i.e., through de-identification or other protective measures. NIH recognizes that certain factors (e.g., legal, ethical, technical) may limit the ability to preserve and share data. Plans should include consideration of these factors, when applicable, in describing the approach to data management and data sharing. NIH encourages the use of established repositories for preserving and sharing scientific data.

Plan Elements: Consider addressing specific elements outlined in DRAFT guidance (see below, Supplemental DRAFT Guidance: Elements of An NIH Data Management and Sharing Plan).

Plan Assessment: The funding NIH ICO will assess the Plan, through the following processes:

- Extramural Awards: Plans will undergo a programmatic assessment by NIH staff within the proposed funding NIH ICO. NIH encourages potential awardees to work with NIH staff to address any potential concerns regarding the Plan prior to submission.
- Contracts: Plans will be included as part of the technical evaluation performed by NIH staff.
- Intramural Research Projects: Plans will be assessed by the Scientific Director (or designee) or Clinical Director (or designee) of the researcher's funding NIH ICO.
- Other funding agreements: Plans will be assessed in the context of other funding agreement mechanisms (e.g., Other Transactions).

CD2H RESPONSE

Recommendation VIa: Substitute text to strengthen statement regarding factors that may impact one's ability to comply with the Policy (2nd paragraph, penultimate sentence):

Replace "Plans should include consideration of these factors, when applicable, in describing the approach to data management and data sharing." with "When such factors are present they must be clearly explained and sufficiently detailed to make it clear to the NIH that data sharing is not possible in these cases."

Recommendation VIb: NIH should provide the infrastructure, including established repositories for preserving and sharing of scientific data and, if need be, provide assistance in using these tools.

A requirement of researchers by the NIH to utilize established repositories for preserving and sharing scientific data requires a significant investment of time and research on the part of the investigator to identify and vet such repositories. In the absence of a data repository administered by the NIH itself, best practice recommendations for the selection of appropriate and established repositories for storing and sharing scientific data should be outlined. Recommendations can follow established guidelines from publishers for identifying and vetting repositories, such as those provided by the Public Library of Science (PLOS) [<https://blogs.plos.org/everyone/2018/03/01/criteria-for-recommended-data-repositories/>] and Data Repository Selection: Criteria That Matter [<https://osf.io/m2bce/>, blog at <https://blog.datacite.org/data-repository-selection-which-criteria-matter/>]. These requirements take into account both data preservation considerations and open access considerations. Recommendations of community-supported and vetted resources for identifying repositories, such as those listed at FAIRsharing.org, would also be helpful.

In addition, the policy can more clearly outline a vision for data sharing compliance. What are the good, better, and best levels of data sharing that the NIH envisions for its funded datasets? Is full open access (deposit-enabled) desired, or creating a catalog record with a data access option to contact the data owner for access? Are any and all points in between acceptable? Encouraging, but not requiring, a basic level of sharing will likely lead to most sharing statements outlining reasons that the data cannot be shared.

An established repository can also take the form of a local institutional repository that has been robustly developed to meet Internet security protocols and to enable data-sharing on multiple levels. Allowance for interoperability through supported metadata-exchange channels can allow the use of local repositories with an option to transfer and migrate data to community-based or public repositories as needed. The Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR) has shepherded a highly relevant and forward-looking initiative that defines behaviors and technologies required for Next Generation Repositories [<http://ngr.coar-repositories.org/>]. This effort is focused on user needs and informed by best practices and standards as a foundation for a distributed, globally-networked infrastructure for scholarly communication, discovery, and innovation.

We wholeheartedly support the assertion from others in the community that support from NIH in the form of interoperability resources/human assistance would be helpful if researchers want to deposit to local or subject repositories and have their metadata and deposited files migrate easily to any NIH-sponsored tool.

Section VII: Compliance and Enforcement (limit: 8000 characters)

During the Funding or Support Period

During the funding period, compliance with the Plan will be determined by the funding NIH ICO. Compliance with the Plan, including any Plan updates, will be reviewed during regular reporting intervals (e.g., at the time of annual Research Performance Progress Reports (RPPRs)) at a minimum.

- Extramural Awards: The Plan will become a Term and Condition of the Notice of Award. Failure to comply with the Terms and Conditions may result in an enforcement action, including additional special terms and conditions or termination of the award, and may affect future funding decisions.
- Contracts: The Plan will become a Term and Condition of the Award, and compliance with and enforcement of the Plan will be consistent with the award and the Federal Acquisition Regulations (FAR), as applicable.
- Intramural Research Projects: Compliance with and enforcement of the Plan will be consistent with applicable NIH policies established by the NIH Office of Intramural Research and the applicable NIH ICO.
- Other funding agreements: Compliance with and enforcement of the Plan will be consistent with applicable NIH policies.

Post Funding or Support Period

After the end of the funding period, non-compliance with the NIH ICO-approved Plan may be taken into account by the funding NIH ICO for future funding decisions for the recipient institution (e.g., as authorized in the NIH Grants Policy Statement, Section 8.5, Special Award Conditions, and Remedies for Noncompliance (Special Award Conditions and Enforcement Actions)).

RESPONSE: No recommendation.

Supplemental DRAFT Guidance: Allowable Costs for Data Management and Sharing (limit: 8000 characters)

NIH recognizes that making data accessible and reusable for other users, while integral to the research process, may require costs above and beyond the routine costs of conducting research. To assist individuals and entities who may be subject to a future NIH Policy for Data Management and Sharing, NIH is proposing supplemental DRAFT guidance regarding potential categories of allowable NIH costs associated with data management and sharing for public comment. NIH is proposing that reasonable, allowable costs may be included in NIH budget requests when associated with:

1. Curating data and developing supporting documentation, include formatting data according to accepted community standards; de-identifying data; attaching metadata to foster discoverability, interpretation, and reuse; and formatting data for transmission and storage at a selected repository for long-term preservation and access.

2. Preserving and sharing data through established repositories, such as data deposit fees and charges necessary for making data available and accessible. When proposing to use a repository that charges recurring fees, budgets may include costs that would be incurred for preserving and sharing data. If the Plan proposes use of multiple repositories, consider including costs associated with use of each proposed repository.
3. Local data management considerations, such as unique and specialized information infrastructure necessary to provide local management, preservation, and access to data, (e.g., before deposit into an established repository). Budget estimates should not include infrastructure costs typically included in institutional overhead (e.g., Facilities and Administrative costs), nor costs associated with the routine conduct of research. Costs associated with collecting or otherwise gaining access to research data (e.g., data access fees) are considered costs of doing research and should not be included in budgets.

CD2H RESPONSE

Recommendation:

- Allowable costs should include funds for data management and sharing
- Make tools, training, and support available and discoverable to individuals and organizations, facilitating more efficient and effective good data practices in support of data management and sharing.
- Consider making infrastructure or supplemental awards available at the institutional level to build or supplement local capacity. Awards could prioritize collaborative teams across key stakeholders in libraries, IT and research computing, and other research-oriented collaborative groups on campus.
- Finally, a great wealth of NIH-funded resources exists in CD2H and across many other efforts that can help to support research data management and data sharing. Support discovery efforts to make these resources, services, and expertise themselves as Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reproducible as possible.

Supplemental DRAFT Guidance: Elements of a NIH Data Management and Sharing Plan (limit: 8000 characters)

To assist those who may be subject to a future NIH Policy for Data Management and Sharing, NIH is proposing supplemental DRAFT guidance regarding elements of a Data Management and Sharing Plan (Plan) for public comment. A Plan should describe in two pages or less the proposed approach to data management and sharing that the specific research will employ. If certain elements of a Plan have not been determined at the time of submission, an entry of “to be determined” may be acceptable if a justification is provided along with a timeline or appropriate milestone at which a determination will be made. Note, NIH does not expect researchers to share all scientific data generated in a study. Elements of a Plan should consider:

1. Data Type: A description of the types and estimated amount of scientific data that will result from NIH-funded or conducted research, which scientific data will be preserved and shared, and the rationale for these decisions. Descriptions may include any additional metadata, information, or documentation about the scientific data that will be made publicly available (e.g., study protocols, data collection instruments). In describing the data Start Printed Page 60402types to be managed, preserved, and shared, consider:
 - Describing data in general terms that address the type and amount/size of scientific data expected to be collected and used in the project (e.g., exome sequences of 20 to 30 gene variants from an estimated 800 cases and fMRI data from ~100 research participants). Descriptions may indicate the data modality (e.g., imaging, genomic, mobile, survey), level of aggregation (e.g., individual, aggregated, summarized), and/or the degree of data processing that has occurred (i.e., how raw or processed the data will be).
 - Providing a rationale for decisions about which scientific data are to be preserved and made available for sharing, taking into consideration scientific utility, validation of results, availability of suitable data repositories, privacy and confidentiality, cost, consistency with community practices, and data security.

- Identifying metadata, other relevant data, and any associated documentation (e.g., study protocols and data collection instruments) which will be made accessible to facilitate interpretation of the scientific data.
 - For scientific data derived from human participants or specimens, outlining plans for providing appropriate protections of privacy and confidentiality (i.e., through de-identification or other protective measures) that are consistent with applicable federal, tribal, state, and local laws, regulations, statutes, guidance, and institutional policies.
2. **Related Tools, Software and/or Code:** An indication of whether specialized tools are needed to access or manipulate shared data to support replication or reuse, and name(s) of the needed tool(s) and software. Consider specifying how needed tools can be accessed, (i.e., open source and freely available, generally available for a fee in the marketplace, or available only from the research team or some other source).
 3. **Standards:** An indication of what standards, if any, will be applied to the scientific data and associated metadata to be collected, including data formats, data identifiers, definitions, unique identifiers, and other data documentation. While many scientific fields have developed and adopted common data standards, others have not. In such cases, the Plan may indicate that no appropriate data standards exist for the data to be collected, preserved, and shared. Provide the name of any data standards or metadata standards proposed for use, considering:
 - Use of existing, widely adopted standards for scientific data and associated metadata. Some examples include: Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium, Minimum Information About a Microarray Experiment, Minimum Information about a high-throughput SEQuencing Experiment, and the Office of the National Coordinator for Health Information Technology Interoperability Standards Advisory.
 - Use of common data elements (CDEs) to facilitate broader and more effective use of scientific data and to advance research across studies. For assistance in identifying NIH-supported CDEs, the NIH has established a Common Data Element (CDE) Resource Portal.
 4. **Data Preservation, Access, and Associated Timelines:** An indication of the timelines for data preservation and access, considering:
 - Where scientific data will be archived to ensure long-term preservation (i.e., which repository(ies)). If scientific data will be archived in an existing data repository(ies), consider providing the name and URL web address of the repository(ies). If an existing data repository(ies) will not be used, consider indicating why not and how scientific data will be preserved and shared.
 - How the scientific data will be findable and whether a persistent unique identifier or other standard indexing tools will be used, and any provisions for maintaining the security and integrity of the scientific data (e.g., encryption and backups).
 - Whether additional considerations are needed to implement the Plan, (e.g., whether permission needs to be sought to use a specific data repository, and from whom).
 - Whether scientific data generated from humans or human biospecimens will be available through unrestricted (made publicly available to anyone) or restricted access (made available only after the requestor has received approval to use the requested scientific data). If the scientific data will be shared through a restricted access mechanism, consider describing the general terms of access for the data.
 - Anticipated timeframes for preserving scientific data, describing if different timelines will apply to different subsets of scientific data, and when the scientific data will be submitted to specified data repositories.
 - When the scientific data will be made available to other users (e.g., researchers and the broader public). In general, scientific data should be made available as soon as practicable, independent of award period and publication schedule. If applicable, consider indicating when scientific data will no longer be available to other users.
 5. **Data Sharing Agreements, Licenses, and Other Use Limitations:** NIH encourages the broadest use of scientific data resulting from NIH-funded or conducted research, consistent with privacy, security, informed consent, and proprietary issues. In describing proposed plans for managing data sharing agreements and other types of arrangements, consider indicating:

- A description of any restrictions imposed by existing agreements that would limit the ability to broadly share scientific data, as well as summarizing what those limitations on sharing or reuse are.
 - Whether the applicant anticipates entering into any agreements that could limit the ability to broadly share scientific data and describe those agreements.
 - Any other considerations that may result in limitations on the ability to broadly share scientific data.
 - How relevant limitations to sharing are consistent with community expectations, and how scientific data will be shared to the maximum extent possible while honoring these limitations.
6. Oversight of Data Management: An indication of the individual(s) who will be responsible for executing various components (e.g., data collection, data analysis, data submission) of the Plan over the course of the research project and the roles of the individual(s) in data management, and a description of the appropriate expertise for oversight.

CD2H RESPONSE

In response to [Response to RFI NOT-OD-19-014](http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2302593), we shared the following Requirements for Data Management and Sharing Plans [<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2302593>]:

The basic components of a DMP. Resources are finite; perfunctory sharing of poorly-documented data does not achieve the objectives of the spirit of FAIR. However, we also recognize that not all data can be held to the same standard. Wherever practicable, data should follow good data practice; for example, data should be published together with methods and factors known to impact reliability. The full “chain-of-custody” should be documented from the generation of data through its safeguarding and analysis. Not only does this provenance help the users of data assess its veracity-- but it also helps ensure attribution, whether to scientists or to members of the public.

Data management and sharing plans should describe a reliable, consistent, and well understood mechanism for recording data and its associated metadata. Supporting “knowledge services” should be described that provide the appropriate shared vocabularies, ontologies and reference information for documenting data. Knowledge services should include information about units, representational forms, scientific methods, domain knowledge, organizations, researchers and ontologies that define the methods and knowledge of the domain itself. This service must be made freely available, reliable and subject to independent verifiability and community correction. A description of the search and retrieval services should also be required, to allow researchers to query, discover and utilize data. The retrieval service must include both the data and its associated pedigree (see attribution, provenance, and reproducibility below) and must provide a mechanism that allows the provenance of derived and enhanced data to be re-entered into the data management plan faithfully and traceably.

Assessment of quality. Data Management and Sharing plans are required for any grant proposals over 500K direct costs/year; however, making them required and scored for all grants is one of the single most impactful changes that the NIH could make. Moreover, we believe that this section should be scored as part of the review criteria. Because most people on NIH review panels are experts in the given specific area of science and not in data management or open science, it would be beneficial for NIH to seek out this expertise for the review panels. It should be noted that often the professional profile of open science experts expands outside the usual background of more typical investigators with R01 funding, and as such, a different approach and criteria for selecting these experts should be created. This may be true for other areas of the review panel as well, but our RFI response is focused exclusively on the Data Management and Sharing plans.

Execution of the data management plans. Throughout the life of a funding award, the data provider/investigator should be evaluated for adherence to the data management and sharing plans by external expert reviewers. Data management and sharing plans should be versioned and updated as the science, community technology, and standards evolve. To encourage investigators to outline effective data management and sharing plans, funders should incentivize grant applicants to include funding allocations within their grant applications to establish partnerships with teams developing

standards or data management systems. This also requires an increase in the overall award to reflect the added burden of data management. Otherwise the data management and sharing plan becomes an unfunded mandate. As well, there should be consequences for project leaders who do not abide by the spirit of their proposed plans.

Considerations regarding data reusability. We urge NIH to consider attributes of data management and sharing that most limit the actual reusability of data. While the FAIR principles have helped to promote awareness, these don't provide guidance on how to actually make data more reusable and therefore useful. We have written extensively about factors that maximize data reusability, specifically for data integrators and third-party users. For example, in response to RFI NOT-OD-16-133 (Metrics to Assess Value of Biomedical Digital Repositories), we wrote about FAIR-TLC, where the T is Traceability, L is licensure, and C is connectedness.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.203295>. There are numerous specific recommendations in this RFI that are relevant here, but we therefore refer the reader to that other document. Finally, data should be openly available for use, in both human and machine-readable formats.

Data licensing and data use agreements. We recommend that the NIH mandate that all publicly funded sources of data, knowledge, or tools be documented with a clearly defined and preferably standard license. [The \(Re\)usable Data Project](#) has evaluated the licensing of 56 NIH publicly funded data resources (including some NIH sources), and has illuminated the fundamental barriers to data science due to a lack of ability to mash-up and redistribute these data. A preprint describing the findings is here: [A Measure of Open Data: A Metric and Analysis of Reusable Data Practices in Biomedical Data Resources](#). This inability to redistribute seemingly "open" data sources limits their potential impact, not only for discovery, but also in for patient care. This problem is so significant, the community wrote a letter to Francis Collins, "[Request for Community partnership in data resource licensing planning](#)".

A change in the Data management and sharing plan seems ideal timing for coordinated improvements to licensing across NIH funded resources. We believe that licensing is one of the most important and overlooked requirements needed to make data reuse a reality. A license MUST be required in all DMPs.

Identifiers. All genes, proteins, variants, phenotypes, diseases, chemicals, species, biosamples etc. should be referenced using appropriate vocabularies/ontologies/reference data. The scientists that generate and publish data are those best positioned to properly annotate it; they should do so using community best practices. Provisioning and management of identifiers should be detailed in the data management and sharing plan; a three-year community coordination effort led to some agreed-upon best practices published in PLoS Biology [<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2001414>] Persons should be referenced by an identifier, with ORCID being the most prominent and most integrated person-level identifier in use. Moreover, organizations should also be referred to by a persistent identifier [<https://ror.community/>]. Resolvers (examples are N2T.net and identifiers.org) should be used to persistently redirect identifiers where they are made public, and details to avoid link-rot should be included in the management plan. Documentation of identifier provisioning, schema, and examples are often lacking, and we would recommend that this be a required component.

Attribution, provenance, and reproducibility. Reproducible science depends in part on knowing what has been specifically performed and by whom. Not only does this hamper reproducibility and evidence for scientific conclusions, it also disincentivizes diverse types of contributions. A data management plan should also document how it plans to include attribution, provenance of the data, and to address any reproducibility aspects (including identification of primary resources, see <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.148>). The goals should be to (1) to give credit where credit is due for everyone - regardless of their discipline, title, or contribution, regardless of whether it fits into narrowly defined construct of success; (2) to enable linking of all research outputs created during a study together, enabling access to data and results (even negative results), tools, and ideas which often remain invisible because they do not appear in a published manuscript, as access helps drive

discovery; (3) facilitate re-use of the information in a variety of ways by all stakeholders (individuals, publishers, scholarly organizations, data repositories, and funding agencies). For example, relationships between people and their products/activities can be used to track research trends; to understand and leverage influences or projects; to promote collaboration and team formation; as recommender systems for scholarly products or methodologies; and to present a complete record of results and research outputs. Fundamentally, the data about the contributions that scholars make should be as open as the data and resources themselves if we really aim to incentivize sharing and open science. The CD2H has completed a number of activities to aid in supporting improved attribution, including the development of a data model and implementation into existing research systems, both with community and stakeholder input and coordination.

Sustainability. While not every DMP need include a business plan, there should be a requirement to address persistence of the data and access to it, as well as the financial support required to do so. DMPs for data about people also need to include indigenous rights as well as the confidentiality of the person, and the sustainability and maintenance for governance rights.